

ALE-SSM: A High-Fidelity Computational Framework for Modeling Wind-Wave-WEC Interaction

This presentation will discuss recent developments in high-fidelity computational fluid-structure interaction (FSI) using the Arbitrary Lagrangian-Eulerian formulation with Skeleton-Based Structural Modeling (ALE-SSM) framework. The development of ALE-SSM was motivated by the need to cost-effectively simulate the nonlinear interactions of wave energy converters (WECs) with fluid motions generated by different sea states, including tropical storms. The development of ALE-SSM intends to reduce the computational size of FSI calculations by using line elements to model the WEC domain, thus reducing the computational cost. ALE-SSM is unique in that it incorporates a geometric model of the physical fluid-WEC interface, which is used to establish a reliable communication between the fluid domain and the line elements. The presentation will discuss the ALE-SSM background and showcase simulations for FSI problems related to WEC motion under the effect of different wave parameters. The effect induced by combined wind and wave flows is also discussed.